

Macrocyclic nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes derived from triethylenetetramine

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Three new macrocyclic ligands 11-chloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (CTCU), 11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (DTCU) and 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[10.10.10.0]dotriacontane (DTCD) are generated in the template condensation of triethylenetetramine with chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and hexachloroethane, respectively. Formulation of the synthesized products $[\text{Ni}(\text{CTCU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{DTCU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DTCU})]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DTCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_6$ and the metal-free ligand hydrochloride DTCU.4HCl has been reported by the elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, melting points and spectral studies.

Recently, we have reported the formation of macrocyclic nickel(II) complex of 11,12-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclotetradecane by template condensation of equimolar amounts of triethylenetetramine and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane. In another approach two nickel(II) complexes of 12,13-benzal, 11,14-dihydroxy-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclotetradeca-10,14-diene and 11,16-dihydroxy-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclohexadeca-10,16-diene derived from 1 : 1, nickel phthalate and adipate complexes, respectively, have been isolated using triethylenetetramine as reagent for cyclization¹. A number of binucleating macrocycles containing one bond linking two macrocyclic rings have been derived from linear tetramines² including triethylenetetramine. Ligands containing more elaborate linkages between the rings have also been synthesized using other tetramines³. A macrocycle with fused rings 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,21-octaazabicyclo[10.10.0]docosane is generated in template condensation between triethylenetetramine and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane in presence of nickel(II)¹. Tris(2-aminoethyl)amine was employed to synthesize a binucleating cage by Lehn *et al.*⁴.

In the present work generation of the macrocycles, 11-chloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (CTCU), 11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (DTCU) and 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[10.10.10.0]dotriacontane (DTCD) (Fig. 1) have been reported in the template condensation of the triethylenetetramine with chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and hexachloroethane, respectively.

Experimental

All chemicals used in the synthesis were reagent grade and were used without further purification. Conductivity

Fig. 1. Suggested structures of the macrocyclic ligands CTCU, DTCU and DTCD.

data of the complexes were recorded using their 0.01 M aqueous solution, with the help of a DDR conductivity meter type 304. Mass spectra were recorded at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. A Jeol D-300 (EI/CI) spectrometer was used for obtaining the mass spectra of the ligand hydrochloride. FTIR spectra were recorded by Shimadzu 8201 PC (4000–350 cm⁻¹) infrared spectrophotometer. The PMR spectra were taken in D₂O solution and recorded on Bruker

DRX 300 (300 MHz FT NMR) using DSS as an internal standard.

Microanalyses for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. For obtaining the nickel(II) and copper(II) contents, the complexes were decomposed⁵ and the metal content was determined by EDTA titration⁶. The ionizable chloride in the samples was determined by conductivity titration⁵.

General synthetic procedure : Template syntheses of nickel(II) or copper(II) complexes were carried out in 500 mL round bottomed flask using 200 mL *n*-butanol as solvent. The macrocyclic complexes were extracted in water and then recovered by concentration, refrigeration and crystallization in water or by treatment with methanol. Finally, the complexes were washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Synthesis of the metal complexes of 11-chloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (CTCU) and 11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (DTCU) : [Ni(CTCU)(H₂O)₂]Cl₂·5H₂O was prepared by heating an equimolar mixture of nickel hydroxide (6.00 g, 64.70 mmol), triethylenetetramine (9.46 g, 64.69 mmol) and chloroform (7.72 g, 64.67 mmol) in 200 mL butanol. The stirred mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The initial mixture containing green precipitate immediately changed to violet within 5 min of heating. After 2 h of continuous heating it changed to a mixture of a red solution and violet precipitate. The content was stirred with 100 mL of water till the precipitate was dissolved. The red aqueous layer was separated from the very light red non-aqueous layer. After concentration and evaporation of the aqueous solution a light brownish-red semi-solid was obtained. The solid was dissolved in 50 mL methanol and stirred. A pink precipitate of the product formed was filtered and the yellowish-red filtrate containing impurities was rejected. The pink precipitate washed with methanol, followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure yielded pink powder of the macrocyclic product, yield 2.44 g.

A 1 : 1 : 1, copper hydroxide : chloroform : triethylenetetramine (copper hydroxide 6.00 g) blue reaction mixture refluxed for 6 h and 30 min, changed into a greenish-blue turbid solution. After stirring the mixture with 100 mL of water, the dirty yellowish-red residue (in very small quantity), non-aqueous brownish-red layer and the bluish-violet aqueous layer were separated as usual. But, concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution did not yield the macrocyclic product.

Aqueous solution of nickel-DTCU or copper-DTCU

complex was obtained as described above for CTCU system, from the equimolar reaction mixture of nickel hydroxide or copper (6.00 g), carbon tetrachloride and triethylenetetramine in *n*-butanol refluxed for 2 h or 1 h and 30 min, respectively. The aqueous yellowish-red solution of nickel system was concentrated and evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a reddish-brown wet powder. The wet powder was dried by pressing between two pieces of filter paper. The process was repeated for 2–3 times (each time taking fresh pieces of paper) till appearance of brownish-yellow spot on filter paper. The yellowish-brown powder was dissolved in 50 mL of methanol. Pinkish-violet fine crystals insoluble in methanol were filtered. Then washing of the crystals of the product [Ni(DTCU)(H₂O)₂]Cl₂ with methanol gave analytically pure complex, yield 2.50 g. Concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution of copper system yielded greenish-grey fine crystals of the product [Cu(DTCU)]Cl₂. The crystals were washed with ether and dried, yield 0.60 g.

Preparation of the hydrochloride of 11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (DTCU.4HCl) : The (11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane)copper(II) chloride ([Cu(DTCU)]Cl₂) (1.00 g, 2.77 mmol) was dissolved in 50 mL water. Concentrated HCl (5 mL, 12 N) was added and the copper(II) ion was removed by passing H₂S gas as described in previous publications^{5,9}. Concentration and evaporation of the resulting aqueous solution yielded fine, yellowish-white hard crystals of ligand hydrochloride DTCU.4HCl. The crystals were finally washed with ether and dried, yield 0.92 g.

Synthesis of the nickel(II) complex of 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[10.10.10]-dotriacontane (DTCD) : Template condensation of triethylenetetramine (7.89 g, 53.95 mmol) and hexachloroethane (4.26 g, 17.99 mmol) in presence of nickel hydroxide (5.00 g, 53.92 mmol), yielded the trimetallic nickel(II) complex [Ni₃(DTCD)(H₂O)₆]Cl₆. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h and the product was extracted in water. After concentration and evaporation under reduced pressure the yellowish-red aqueous solution yielded a reddish-brown hygroscopic solid. 100 mL of methanol was added to the reddish-brown hygroscopic solid and then stirred for 5 min. The pink powder of the product was filtered and the brownish-red filtrate was rejected. The product was again washed with methanol followed by ether and dried, yield, 1.68 g.

An attempt to isolate products from 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1, nickel hydroxide : triethylenetetramine : hexachloroethane mixtures was not successful. Each mixture (containing 5.00

g nickel hydroxide) was refluxed for 2 h and 30 min. Similarly, no product could be synthesized from 1 : 1 : 1, 2 : 2 : 1 and 3 : 3 : 1, copper hydroxide : triethylenetetramine : hexachloroethane mixture (each containing 6.00 g copper hydroxide) refluxed for 2 h, 2 h and 30 min, and 3 h, respectively.

Results and discussion

Template condensation of triethylenetetramine with chlorocarbons, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride or hexachloroethane in presence of nickel hydroxide yields different macrocyclic ligand complexes. Eleven-membered ring product is generated in the refluxed mixture containing equimolar amounts of nickel hydroxide, triethylenetetramine and chloroform or carbon tetrachloride. Cyclization proceeds with the condensation of the chlorocarbons with nickel-coordinated triethylenetetramine. The four aza donors of the ligands 11-chloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (CTCU) and 11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (DTCU) generated in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride systems, respectively, are coordinated to nickel. Replacement of nickel hydroxide by copper hydroxide, in carbon tetrachloride system also leads to generation of DTCU macrocycle.

A trinuclear complex was obtained from the mixture containing nickel hydroxide, triethylenetetramine and hexachloroethane in 3 : 3 : 1 molar ratio. Three moles of nickel-coordinated triethylenetetramine condensed with one mole of hexachloroethane. Three nickel(II) ions are accommodated in three separate twelve-membered rings of the generated ligand 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[10.10.10.0]dotriacontane (DTCD).

All the complexes and the ligand hydrochloride DTCU-4HCl were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, conductivity measurements and spectral studies. The results of elemental analyses reported in Table 1 indicate the stoichiometry which is in agreement with the formulation given. Evidence for cyclization is demonstrated by the

absence of absorption bands that may be attributed to either free or coordinated NH_2 groups^{1,5,7}.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectrum of nickel-CTCU complex indicates the absence of bands due to NH_2 group. A band attributed to only secondary amine appears at 3161 cm^{-1} . This suggests that the complex is a macrocyclic molecule. The $\delta(\text{N-H})$ appears as a medium but very sharp band at 1595 cm^{-1} . A strong band at 1072 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the C-N stretching vibrations. Medium bands at 2932 (sharp), 2878 (sharp) and 1462 cm^{-1} (very sharp) are attributed to C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring modes of vibration, respectively. Bands associated with coordinated water at the frequencies (cm^{-1}), 3234 (strong, very sharp), 1649 (weak, very sharp), 770 (very weak), 667 (medium, sharp), 580 (weak) and 540 (weak, very sharp) are due to $\nu(\text{O-H})$, $\delta(\text{O-H})$, rocking, wagging, twisting modes of water molecules and $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$, respectively⁸. Many other bands are characteristic of the whole complex molecule. A very weak band at 446 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ mode. There is close correspondence in the infrared spectra of nickel complexes with CTCU and DTCU in $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The $\nu(\text{N-H})$, $\nu(\text{C-H})$, $\delta(\text{C-H})$, $\nu(\text{C-N})$ or $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ (430 cm^{-1}) bands in nickel-DTCU complex are at lower energy as compared the corresponding bands in nickel-CTCU complex. Similarly, the different bands associated with coordinated water are also at lower energy except the $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ which is at identical frequency (540 cm^{-1}). The N-H bending band is seen at 1600 cm^{-1} .

In the infrared spectrum of the copper-DTCU complex the weak N-H mode of secondary amine group is at lower frequency (3140 cm^{-1}) than in nickel-DTCU or Ni-CTCU complex. The compound exhibits $\delta(\text{N-H})$ vibration at 1565 cm^{-1} . The C-H asymmetric and symmetric stretching and $\delta(\text{C-H})$ bands are seen at 2950 (medium, broad), 2880 (very weak) and 1450 cm^{-1} (medium), respectively. The weak but very sharp and very weak but sharp bands at 1020 and 440 cm^{-1} , respectively, are attributed to $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$. Absence of bands due to water molecule support the structure of the complex. The metal-free DTCU hydrochloride exhibits medium, weak and very weak bands at 2945 , 2850 and 1412 cm^{-1} assigned to C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring vibrations, respectively. The N-H stretching and bending modes appear as very weak bands at the frequencies 3192 and 1562 cm^{-1} , respectively. The $\nu(\text{C-N})$ band is seen at 1090 cm^{-1} . The weak or very weak peaks at 2500 , 2402 , 2340 and 2208 cm^{-1} are associated with the amine hydrochloride groups of ligand. Many other bands are the characteristics of the whole ligand molecule.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data for the macrocyclic compounds

Compd.	Colour (Colour at D.p.)	Yield (%) (M.p. °C)	Λ_M (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Found (Calcd.) %					Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
				C	H	N	Ni/Cu	Cl ^c	
[Ni(CTCU)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ ·5H ₂ O NiC ₇ H ₃₁ N ₄ O ₇ Cl ₃	Pink (brown) ^a	8.40 (2.44)	266	18.71 (18.75)	6.98 (6.98)	12.48 (12.50)	13.13 (13.09)	15.87 (15.81)	– (448.5)
[Ni(DTCU)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ NiC ₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	Pinkish violet (black)	9.84 (232) ^d	270	21.46 (21.40)	5.12 (5.14)	14.24 (14.27)	15.01 (14.95)	18.01 (18.05)	– (392.8)
[Cu(DTCU)]Cl ₂ CuC ₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ Cl ₄	Greenish-grey black	12.59 (232) ^d	275	23.20 (23.25)	4.46 (4.47)	15.52 (15.50)	17.64 (17.57)	19.54 (19.61)	– (361.6)
DTCU·4HCl C ₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ Cl ₂ ·4HCl	Yellowish white (black)	89.19 (180) ^d	–	22.48 (22.54)	5.40 (5.42)	15.01 (15.02)	–	38.10 (38.02)	368.0 (373.0)
[Ni(DTCD)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₆ Ni ₃ C ₂₀ H ₆₀ N ₁₂ O ₆ Cl ₆	Pink (black) ^b	9.82 (238)	640	25.12 (25.18)	6.36 (6.35)	17.60 (17.63)	18.54 (18.47)	22.38 (22.30)	– (953.8)

^aBrown at 250°C; ^bBlack at 270°C; ^cIonizable chloride ion, ^dDecomposition.

Fig. 2. Suggested structures of the Ni-CTCU, Ni-DTCU, Ni-DTCD and Cu-DTCU complexes.

The vibration frequencies due to N–H of the secondary amine and the C–H in the infrared spectrum of the trinuclear nickel-DTCD complex are: $\nu(\text{N-H})$, 3150 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(\text{N-H})$, 1956 cm^{-1} ; $\nu(\text{C-H})$, 2925 (asymmetric), 2875 (symmetric) and $\delta(\text{C-H})$, 1460 cm^{-1} . A weak but very sharp band at 500

cm^{-1} is attributed to $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ modes. Coordination of water is supported by the presence of bands at 3220 (strong and sharp), 1642, 760 (medium, very sharp), 666 (strong and sharp), 600 (very weak but sharp) and 570 cm^{-1} (medium but very sharp). These bands are assigned to O–H stretching, bending, rocking, wagging, twisting and $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ modes.

Comparison at DTCU, CTCU and DTCD systems : The nickel or copper ions are coordinated to four aza groups of DTCU or CTCU in the cavity consisting bridge combination 2,2,2,1 (Fig. 2). In the nickel complexes the $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration frequency follows the order : CTCU > DTCU. A lower value in case of DTCU complex is expected due to presence of two Cl atoms in the ligand which reduce the Ni–N electron density. This effect is comparatively poor in the CTCU complex. The $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibration frequency in these complexes is comparable. The $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ vibration at 540 cm^{-1} in each system shows that coordinating tendency of H₂O molecules to the complex is identical. Further, the C–N stretching vibration order (CTCU > DTCU) is expected due to stronger inductive effect by two Cl atoms in CTCU. The band order : Cu–N > Ni–N is shown by the stretching metal nitrogen vibration frequencies in copper and nickel complexes of DTCU. In addition, the $\nu(\text{N-H})$ or $\nu(\text{C-N})$ vibration frequencies as expected follow the order : Ni > Cu.

Unlike CTCU or DTCU (planar molecule), the

macrocyclic DTCD is a three-dimensional molecule where each smaller ring consists a bridge combination of 2,2,2,2. Comparatively much suitable bridge combination (providing a larger ring size) for complex formation and absence of electron withdrawing Cl atoms in DTCD are responsible for a high Ni–N bond order in its nickel complex.

Further, stronger H₂O coordination in Ni-DTCD complex as shown by $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{O})$ vibration (570 cm^{-1}) is probably associated with the three-dimensional structure of the ligand where coordinated water molecules are expected to be partially trapped between two rings.

PMR spectra :

DTDU and DTCD systems : In the PMR spectra of the nickel(II) complexes with DTCU and DTCD, the signals at 4.78 and 4.68 ppm, respectively are expected for NH proton resonances. Further, for the DTCU complex, a hump is observed in 4.10–2.25 ppm region which is assigned to CH₂ proton resonances. But, in the DTCD complex a broad doublet expected for methylene protons appeared in 4.00–1.80 ppm region. The coordinated water resonances in both the systems are obscured by the NH or CH₂ signals.

Mass spectra :

The determination of molecular weight of DTCU.4HCl by mass spectra has been very useful in completing its characterization. The highest mass peak found in the spectrum of DTCU.4HCl (by EIMS) is at m/z values close to its molecular ion (Table I). The peak is very weak and is comparable to those of many earlier reported aza macrocycles⁹. The slightly low m/z value is probably associated with the mass lost (H) due to fragmentation of the molecular ion. The fragmentation pattern of the molecule is shown by many mass peaks at m/z 44, 70, 97, 112, 140, 166, 194, 216, 253, 269, 280, 303, 318 and 368.

Solubility, conductivity and other data :

In view of their ionic nature the complexes and the ligand hydrochloride DTCU.4HCl are highly soluble in water. Also, they are generally soluble in many other polar solvents like methanol, ethanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. The molar conductivity and the number of ionizable chloride ions recorded in Table I support the ionic nature. [Ni(CTCU)]

(H₂O)₂]Cl₂.5H₂O, [Ni(DTCU)(H₂O)₂]Cl₂ and [Cu(DTCU)]Cl₂ are 2 : 1 electrolytes exhibiting molar conductance 266, 270 and 275 $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-2}\text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. The molar conductance value for nickel-DTCD complex (Table 1) is consistent with 6 : 1 electrolyte. The copper complex of DTCU is greenish-grey. But, the nickel complexes of CTCU or DTCD and DTCU are pink and pinkish-violet, respectively. The colour of the DTCU.4HCl is yellowish-white. The compounds are thermally stable.

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